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MEETING ABSTRACTS FROM MSA DUBROVNIK 2020 CONFERENCE

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Invited speakers

S1

PREVALENCE OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AMONG ADOLESCENTS FROM 105 COUNTRIES

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Physical activity (PA) is a beneficial health behaviour. To present the worldwide, regional, and national prevalence of PA participation in adolescents. The study was based on surveys of adolescents' population from several countries worldwide. The sample comprised 520,533 adolescents (251,788 boys, 268,745 girls), from 105 countries and regions. Most adolescents engaged in PA up to 3 times/week (57.1%). The prevalence of engaging in PA every day decreases over the age from 28.2% at age of 11-12 years (95% CI: 27.4, 29.0) to 21.2% at age of 16-17 years (95% CI: 20.3, 22.0) among boys, and from 19.4% (95% CI: 18.5, 20.2) to 11.1% (95% CI: 10.1, 12.0) among girls. For boys and girls who engaged in PA 5-6 times/day, the prevalence increases from countries with the lowest human development index to countries with the highest. Cambodia (7.3%, 95% CI: 3.8, 10.8), Philippines (7.7%, 95% CI: 5.6, 9.7), Sudan (8.8%, 95% CI: 4.7, 12.9), Timor-Leste (8.9%, 95% CI: 5.5, 12.3), and Afghanistan (10.1%, 95% CI: 6.1, 14.1) were the countries with the lowest prevalence of sufficient PA. National, regional and worldwide data on the prevalence of PA in adolescents highlights the importance of improving the global levels of PA, especially in girls.

S2

FOOTBALL REFEREES - THE THIRD TEAM

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Football game is getting faster every day and players' skills and abilities are improving with every new generation of players. Therefore, physical fitness is very important for football referees. Referees need to be in good physical shape to keep up with a modern football pace. The physiological aspects and movement patterns of football referees during football game are a well-researched topic during last decade. Also, importance of regular training in football referees is well emphasized in scientific publications, so training sessions are monitored by national football federations and UEFA/FIFA. High physical load of the game, and the stress it generates on the cardio-vascular and musculoskeletal systems can increase a risk of injury. Accordingly, appropriate medical status and low injury occurrence are one of the most important aspects of successful refereeing. Medical status, risk factors, type and frequency of injuries among football referees are recent research areas. Psychological and emotional aspects of refereeing are also very important. Being a football referee is not just being close to the ball. Coping skills (dealing with game stress, stress of making mistake, influence of the referee's decision on players, coach staff or public) are very important. Decision-making process in football referees is intertwined with high level of interaction with players, high physical demands and lot of cues during football match. Some of these aspects are discussed in this paper.

S3

NO CHILD'S LAND: SHRINKING OF CHILDREN'S ROAMING SPACE AND ITS IMPLICATIONS FOR PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERIPHERAL BLOOD CIRCULATION INDICATORS IN STAYER SWIMMERS UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF THE HYPOXIC GAS ENVIRONMENT AND MIDDLE MOUNTAINS

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Competitive activity in the midlands places high demands on the state of the cardiovascular system of swimmers-stayers. Modern strategies for the prevention of cardiovascular disorders in swimmers-stayers for competitive activity in the midlands are based mainly on the assessment of systemic hemodynamics, excluding microcirculation. The aim of this study is to review the available literature on studies related to the state of the cardiovascular system of swimmers-stayers under conditions of a hypoxic gas environment and midlands. Specific key words "exercise", "swimmers", "stayer", "hypoxia", "midlands", and "mountains" were used to search relevant electronic databases, such as PubMed, Web of Science and Scopus. The process of adaptation and change in functional indicators in swimmers-stayers, characterizing their physical performance and the functioning of external respiration, occurs mainly due to the expansion of the range of application of training tools and methods. The endless expansion of the range of application of training tools and methods can lead to serious disturbances in the functioning of their cardiovascular system. Studies have shown that microcirculation in swimmers-stayers during the load of different capacities in the midlands and hypoxic gas environment have a similar dynamics. This allows us to better diagnose the state of the cardiovascular system in athletes and more accurately assess the reaction of their body to a load of different power in the midlands.

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BODY MASS INDEX MODULATES GRIP STRENGTH DEVELOPMENT

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Grip strength (GS) has been considered as a reliable indicator of general strength in healthy children. Notwithstanding, recent studies suggested the use of grip-to-BMI ratio, because GS approximation likely depends on BMI, and in this regard, the approximation of GS development trajectories. The study aimed to investigate the confounding effects of BMI on GS in the function of age in healthy children, and in turn potentially justify the grip-to-BMI ratio usefulness. This study included boys (n=493) and girls (n=664) aged from 4 to 7 years and measured their body height(cm), weight(kg), BMI(kg/m²) and GS of dominant-hand using Bulb dynamometer (psi). The multilevel linear regression model tested the hypotheses. Mean-GS tended to linear increase with age (-1.796+0.889AGE; R=.478; p<.001; B:95%CI .795to.983). However, age influence was significantly lower when BMI was deemed in the model (-4.772+0.841AGE+0.2BMI; R=.543, p<.001), because mean-GS tended to be higher with higher BMI (-0.163+0.24BMI; R=.303; p<.001; B:95%CI .196to.284). When the general strength is assessed using grip strength in healthy children, the approximation of general strength and its trajectories should be made by cautions because many factors influence GS performance and development. A possible solution may be grip-to-BMI ratio, but according to previous

studies, lean body mass, and fat mass also modulate GS across all ages.

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SPORTS NUTRITION KNOWLEDGE EVALUATION CONDUCTED ON MONTENEGRIN FIRST LEAGUE OF MEN'S HANDBALL PLAYERS

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Besides numerous factors that affect athletes' physical fitness and success in different sports branches, an adequate nutrition plays an important role. The aim of this research was evaluation of Montenegrin first league of men's handball knowledge of sports nutrition basics. This study encompassed 37 professional athletes in Montenegrin first league of men's handball, aged from 16 to 38. The research was based on a closed-ended questionnaire consisting of 17 questions and designed per questionnaires already available in literature (Rosenbloom, Jonnalagadda & Skinner, 2002; Zawila, Steib & Hoogenboom, 2003; Juzwiak & Ancona-Lopez, 2004; Ersoy, 2004; Ozdogan & Ozcelik, 2011). As for descriptive statistical methods, the measures of central tendency, arithmetic mean and median were used. Statistical analysis was accomplished by SPSS 17.0 software. 48.33% of respondents answered the questions correctly, 39.90% answered wrongly, and 11.77% stated they did not know the answer to the question, implying thereby that 51.67% of respondents did not have a basic knowledge of sports nutrition. Based on acquired results, we can conclude that knowledge of sports nutrition is below the satisfactory level. It is necessary to work on continuous education on importance of proper sports nutrition and impact on health and performance of all athletes as well as to focus future researches in this area on a bigger sample of professional athletes so as to obtain more accurate results and provide recommendations in this area.

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SPECIFICITY OF TESTING MAXIMAL OXYGEN CONSUMPTION IN KAYAKERS

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The purpose of this study was to determine the difference in aerobic capacity in athletes (kayakers) and non-athletes, and also to determine the difference in aerobic capacity in kayakers comparing results on a bicycle ergometer and kayak ergometer. The study included 30 male subjects (15 kayakers and 15 non-athletes), for which the following parameters were measured: body weight, body height, Body Mass Index, body fat percentage, dynamometric measurements of muscle strength, spirometric parameters and aerobic capacity. There was no statistically significant difference in body height, body weight and BMI between kayakers and non-athletes (p>0,05) and also no statistically significant difference in VO₂ results for kayakers on bicycle and kayak ergometer (p>0,05). There was a statistically significant difference in aerobic capacity on bicycle ergometers in advantage of kayakers (p<0,01). The group of kayakers have showed statistically higher values of aerobic capacity in comparison to non-athletes on bicycle ergometer. In comparison of results on a bicycle and kayak ergometer for kayakers there was no statistically significant difference.